

UDC: 330.341.1:338.43:047.44

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10624052

METHODICAL PRINCIPLES OF ECONOMIC EVALUATION OF INNOVATION PROCESSES IN THE AGRO-INDUSTRIAL COMPLEX

Oleksandr Hutorov

Doctor of Economics, professor, leading researcher

Department of Geoinformation Technologies and Economic Research,
Institute of climate-oriented agriculture of the National Academy of Agrarian
Sciences of Ukraine

ORCID ID: 0000-0003-0688-9413

Olena Hutorova

Doctor of Economics, Associate Professor, Associate Professor of the Department of
Management, Business and Administration,

State Biotechnological University

ORCID ID: 0000-0003-4705-5482

Abstract. The article discloses the essence of assessing the efficiency of innovation processes in the agro-industrial complex, which provides for the solution of a set of tasks regarding: selection and justification of the strategic direction of research; definition of criteria and a system of evaluation indicators that will allow to specifically determine technological, economic, social and environmental efficiency; assessment of the influence of factors on the efficiency of agricultural enterprises, as well as the choice of an effective method of implementation of innovation activity. The methodological foundations of this process are set out and directions for increasing the innovative activity of enterprises of the agro-industrial complex in the market conditions of management are presented.

The work deepens the existing and develops new theoretical, methodological, practical provisions and recommendations for investment support of the agro-industrial complex. As a result of a comprehensive analysis of the existing methods for assessing the efficiency of innovation processes, the optimal composition of

criteria and relevant indicators of evaluation has been allocated, the practical application of which has allowed to identify a number of fundamental shortcomings: narrow target orientation of evaluation, identity of methodological foundations for assessing the effectiveness of innovation and investment activities, lack of normative values of indicators, which necessitates the development of a methodical approach to assessing the effectiveness of innovation Activity.

For the economic substantiation of the expediency of development and financing of work on the creation of scientific products (innovative project), the article deepens the existing and develops new theoretical, methodological, practical provisions and recommendations for calculating the indicators of efficiency of innovation processes, the sequence of which is proposed to be distributed by stages.

The criteria of efficiency at the stage of mastering innovations (innovations) in production are: technological renewal of production, which contributes to increasing its technological and economic efficiency; growth of labor productivity and social efficiency of production; increase in output per unit of production area; improvement of financial indicators of production and growth of the actual mass of profits; preservation of the normal ecological and nature conservation situation. The efficiency of innovation activity is proposed to be understood as its characteristic, which reflects the effectiveness and reveals the degree of completeness and quality of achievement of the set goals with the help of a system of indicators.

The practical use of the proposed methodical recommendations will allow domestic agro-industrial enterprises to carry out a comprehensive assessment of the efficiency of innovation activity, to increase the scientific validity of managerial decisions on the formation and provision of innovation activity in a changing market environment.

Keywords: innovations, innovation process, agro-industrial complex, innovation activity, innovation project, economic assessment, efficiency, performance indicators.

Introduction. The assessment of the innovative process and the determination of its effectiveness should be conducted both overall and at its individual stages. The necessity of such an approach is justified by the fact that the implementation of the innovation process requires certain financial resources and constant monitoring of their expenditure and profitability not only at its final stage but also at all intermediate stages. The results of step-by-step assessment can serve as a basis for determining the effectiveness of the entire innovation process: from the inception of the idea, scientific research, and innovation creation to its implementation by farmers and the achievement of a certain additional effect directly in production [1].

Review of existing research on the topic. Innovative activities in the agricultural sector have been the subject of detailed research for quite some time. Questions related to defining the connection between the regularities of innovation development, real needs of the innovation process, economic relationships between developers and consumers of innovative products, and the impact of innovations on the economic development of agricultural enterprises, regions, and the country's agro-industrial complex as a whole, have drawn special interest [2].

Various aspects of innovation development in the economy, innovation management, and the evaluation of the effectiveness of innovation processes in the economy and the agro-industrial complex have been explored in the works of leading domestic and foreign scientists such as L.L. Antonyuk, V.M. Heyets, N.P. Denysenko, P. Drucker, S.M. Ilyashenko, N.V. Krasnokutska, I.M. Kuksa, Yu.O. Lupenko, V.M. Onegin, P.G. Pererva, R. Ratvel, H. Riggs, P.T. Sabluk, V.S. Savchuk, V.P. Seminozhenko, B. Twiss, V.G. Fedorenko, H. Hartman, J. Schumpeter, O.M. Yastremska, and others. The analysis of published works and the practice of economic activities of domestic agricultural enterprises indicate insufficient development of fundamentally important issues regarding the peculiarities of implementing the innovation process and forming a comprehensive system for evaluating the effectiveness of innovative activities.

At present, the issue of evaluating innovative processes is quite relevant,

leading to a large number of proposed methods, criteria, and indicators in the scientific literature. In particular, significant contributions to the development of theoretical and methodological approaches to the economic evaluation of the innovation process have been made by scholars such as Hnatenko I.A. [3], Koyuda P.M., Sheyko I.A. [4], Levitska I.V., Postova V.V. [5], Lykholet S.I. [6], Lopatinska Yu.V. [7], Lupenko Yu.O., Kropyvko M.F., Zakharchuk O.V. [8], Mykityuk P.P. [9], Orlova-Kurylova O.V. [10], Seniv B., Korol V. [11], Kharyv P.S. [12], Chorna M.V., Glukhova S.V. [13], and others. However, it is necessary to identify alternative assessment methods that would be reliable, accessible, comparable, easily calculable, and cover all stages of innovation implementation (planning, production preparation, production, and implementation). The relevance of the problem of evaluating the effectiveness of innovative processes, its insufficient theoretical and methodological development, and practical application by domestic agricultural enterprises of the agro-industrial complex determined the choice of the research topic and direction.

Main Part. The main task of the economic evaluation of the innovation process lies in comparing the total costs of scientific research and innovation creation, as well as their dissemination and application in production, with the acquisition of additional production or income from the innovation, i.e., the development of this innovation.

Both the goals and methods of evaluating the innovation process at its individual stages will be different. They must fully correspond to the nature and the main target function of each stage, which will determine the need to choose both evaluation criteria and the formation of a certain system of evaluation indicators.

In the process of evaluating a particular innovation, not only the beneficial result, i.e., the total amount of income (absolute efficiency), should be considered, but also its increase compared to the analog before the innovation development (comparative efficiency). It is crucial to determine the useful life term, both for the creation of innovation in science and its application in production. For different types of innovations, these terms will differ significantly.

For a step-by-step evaluation of the innovation process, it is necessary to clearly distinguish its stages. The generalized innovation process in the agro-industrial complex can be reduced to three main stages: innovation creation, innovation dissemination, and innovation application by producers. At all stages, the efficiency of the process implementation will undoubtedly depend primarily on providing specific intellectual, material, and financial resources for it.

Studies show that the most labor-intensive and costly stage in the structure of the innovation process is the creation of innovations. At this stage, the main attention should be paid to minimizing the time required for innovation creation, as one of the main factors in cost reduction. Equally important is increasing the novelty level of the innovation and maximizing its superiority in key indicators over the traditional analog currently used in production. This can be achieved by comparing projected (projected) indicators with actual ones.

The organization of systematic control over the effectiveness of scientific research requires constant comprehensive economic evaluation of scientific and technical products. The purpose of such evaluation is to identify the advantages and disadvantages of new technologies under development, their variants, various constructive solutions, as well as to determine the economic efficiency of other types of scientific and technical products.

In accordance with the tasks facing the industry as a whole and applied research in particular, it is important to determine the economic effect of research and improve methods for measuring the economic evaluation of scientific projects. The significance of this approach lies in the fact that even at the stage of initiating large-scale work and allocating financial resources for their implementation, there is an objective opportunity to assess the feasibility of research and scientific-technical developments.

Such evaluations are based on entirely different objective requirements that arise due to the conditions of forming and developing a market economy, where factors of socio-economic and techno-technological development will be manifested.

Fundamental changes in economic relations, caused by agrarian reform, determine the need for theoretical verification and practical testing of new methods for evaluating the economic effect of research.

The development of new approaches is also driven by a change in the system of economic relations between developers and consumers of scientific and technical products, leading to a fundamental reorganization of its participants. In the pre-reform period, only the state, represented by scientific institutions or enterprises, was involved in scientific and technical activities. Now, various intermediaries such as financial companies, funds, banks, and other commercial and non-commercial organizations are gradually joining them.

Experience shows that state institutions, research organizations, and commercial enterprises feel the need for new approaches to conduct objective calculations of the economic effect of scientific developments, economic justifications of scientific projects, and a more purposeful selection of research topics that form scientific and technical programs and subprograms at regional and sectoral levels.

To obtain data on the economic justification of the feasibility of developing and financing work on creating scientific products (innovative projects), a series of calculations should be conducted, the sequence of which is distributed by stages.

Stage 1: Initial data for calculations - expenditures of state funds; expenditures of the developer's own funds and other sources.

Stage 2: Calculation of annual economic benefits.

Stage 3: Determination of the total profit of the developer.

Stage 4: Calculation of indicators of economic efficiency of development.

Stage 5: Determination of the feasibility of funding work on the creation of scientific and technical developments.

To conduct calculations, it is necessary to have initial data, including the projected duration of the work, the number of stages (usually by years), the current reporting year, the amount of the financed part of the work for previous years, if any,

the necessary expenses for the continuation and completion of the work, sources of funding, etc.

Next, the total costs from various sources of funding are determined, and the expected annual economic effect of developing scientific and technical products is calculated using the industry methodology.

The next stage is the calculation of profits for the years of implementation of scientific and technical products, determining the additional profit of the producer.

Given the complexity of the stages of the innovation process, when choosing criteria for their evaluation, it is not necessary to strive for a single criterion. It is essential to orient towards a multi-criteria approach to determine the efficiency of a particular stage of the process.

At the stage of creating innovations, the main criteria for their evaluation are the value of the developed innovation, the degree of its novelty and compliance with the modern world level; the predicted increase in gross production and improvement of its quality indicators; maximum resource savings and cost reduction per unit of production.

At the stage of innovation dissemination, the primary criterion for evaluating the innovation process is the maximum efficiency of informing manufacturers about new knowledge and scientific and technological achievements through various channels of dissemination. These channels include the training and retraining of personnel, the implementation of management functions at all levels, an information and advisory service system, and the organization of special promotion of innovations through scientific organizations and the media. The faster information about the created innovations, ready for implementation in production, is communicated to manufacturers, the more effectively this stage of the innovation process functions.

The criteria for effectiveness at the stage of implementing innovations in production include technological modernization of production, contributing to the enhancement of its technological and economic efficiency; an increase in labor

productivity and social efficiency of production; an increase in the volume of output per unit of production area; improvement of financial indicators of production and an increase in actual profit; and the preservation of a normal environmental and conservation situation.

Based on these criteria, a system of evaluation indicators is developed, allowing for a specific determination of technological, economic, social, and environmental efficiency.

At the initial stage of the innovation process, it is crucial to provide a preliminary assessment of the created innovation before its implementation in production. The main goal here is to determine the value of the innovation, its degree of novelty, and its conformity to the global level.

The value of the created innovation resulting from intellectual work is determined by the increase in relevant knowledge compared to their current level, the prospects for their dissemination, and the potential contribution to the development of the industry and the improvement of production efficiency.

For the evaluation of scientific and technical products, the following system of indicators should be used: the level of novelty (high, medium, insufficient); the level of value for science (high, medium, insufficient); the level of value for production (high, medium, insufficient); the degree of compliance with domestic achievements (higher, at the same level, lower); the degree of compliance with foreign achievements (higher, at the same level, lower); the level of demand for the given scientific and technical product (high, medium, insufficient).

The evaluation of the innovation process at the stage of development and widespread use of innovations is carried out by highlighting four main types of efficiency: technological, economic, social, and environmental.

To determine the technological efficiency of using scientific and technical products, indicators reflecting the degree of use of land, labor, and material resources in the production process are applied. These indicators include, among others, an increase in the yield of agricultural crops, an increase in livestock (poultry)

productivity, a reduction in energy intensity in agricultural production, an increase in gross agricultural production in constant prices per 1 ha of agricultural land, per employee, per 1000 UAH of fixed assets, an increase in gross plant production in constant prices per 1 ha of agricultural land, per 1 ha of arable land, an increase in gross production of livestock products in constant prices per head of livestock, per 1 ha of fodder area, an increase in the production of specific types of livestock products per 1 ha of agricultural land, per 1 ha of arable land, an increase in gross production in constant prices per unit of additional resources spent.

To determine the economic efficiency of using innovative products, indicators that indicate an increase in resource conservation, labor productivity, energy intensity, capital intensity of production, and its competitiveness are used.

Specifically, these indicators include: an increase in gross production in actual prices, commodity production, profit, per unit of area or head of livestock, per unit of labor, as well as assets of agricultural production; a reduction in production costs (by types); an increase in production profitability (by types of products); growth in total (overall) profitability; an increase in the value of gross production in current prices, commodity production, and profit per: 1 ha of agricultural land, 1 ha of arable land, 1 average worker, 1 person-hour, 1000 UAH of fixed assets.

To determine the social efficiency of using innovative products, indicators reflecting a decrease in injuries, improvement of working conditions, an increase in the standard of living for workers, the level of consumption of food products, goods of public consumption, housing provision, and the development of the health care and medical services industry are applied. Social efficiency indicators characterize the degree of achievement of population living standards.

The system of social efficiency indicators consists of the following groups: population income (aggregate and monetary income, main sources of income); living conditions of the population (housing, healthcare, education, culture and arts, social services, transportation and communication, environmental and crime situation); labor market (labor resources, working conditions, employment); demographic

processes (birth rate, mortality); social stratification of the population (differentiation of the population by income level, subsistence minimum, poverty, extreme poverty).

To determine indicators of ecological efficiency in using innovative products, emissions and waste into the environment (water, land, forest resources; air basin; wildlife) are taken into account. Evaluations include fully or partially waste-free technologies, the degree of waste utilization in production, the organization of closed-loop water supply, low-waste and waste-free production. The assessment also considers technologies in terms of transitioning from a nature-processing type of production to processes close to natural ones, with a closed material and energy cycle or a reduction in the processing volumes of natural resources.

Based on this, the system of ecological efficiency indicators reflects primary (natural) indicators of reducing environmental pollution, improving its condition, and final socio-ecological efficiency (increasing the ecological standard of living, environmental effect, and eco-economic effect).

The methods for assessing the effectiveness of innovative processes differ in that they should include indicators reflecting the overall integrated effect of creating, producing, and functioning innovations, allowing for the determination of the contribution of each participant in the innovation process. The simplest integrated indicator for assessing the innovation process as a whole can be the profitability of expenses related to the creation and development of innovations, expressed in the amount of net income obtained per 1 UAH of additional expenses related to the creation and development of innovations.

Conclusions. The current pace of innovation development in the domestic agricultural sector, despite some revival in this activity, cannot be considered satisfactory. There is a significant gap between Ukraine and developed countries in the technological level of agro-industrial production, and overcoming it without the implementation of large-scale nationwide measures will be impossible.

One of the important tasks of today is the regulation of the processes of implementing ready-made developments into production, carried out by research

organizations for the agro-industrial complex. The mechanism for transferring such developments to agricultural enterprises is not clearly defined and, as multi-year practice shows, is not yet operational.

Improving the innovation management system in the agro-industrial complex should be comprehensive, covering the entire spectrum of aspects of this activity in the agri-food sector: from research and development, experimental verification of scientific results to implementation in production, and performance evaluation. Enhancing the substantiation and effectiveness of state interventions in the management of innovation activities in the agro-industrial complex could contribute to identifying this issue as one of the priority directions in scientific research on agricultural issues. This would provide a certain impetus to the activation of innovative activities in the industry, promoting the acceleration of scientific and technological progress, and increasing the efficiency of agro-industrial production.

In recent years, the issue of economic stimulation of innovation activities in the agro-industrial complex has become particularly relevant. Stimulation should cover all stages of the innovation process: from the inception of the idea and conducting fundamental and applied research to the development of its results in production and achieving a certain effect while satisfying the mutual interest of both the scientist and the producer.

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